

Less Is More: Partial versus Full Resuscitative Endovascular Balloon Occlusion of the Aorta in Trauma

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Introduction

Traumatic haemorrhage remains a leading cause of preventable mortality worldwide. Resuscitative Endovascular Balloon Occlusion of the Aorta (REBOA) is increasingly used to control non-compressible torso haemorrhage; however, full occlusion is associated with significant ischemic and reperfusion-related complications. Partial REBOA (pREBOA) was introduced to preserve distal perfusion while maintaining proximal haemodynamic support. Direct comparative evidence between partial and full REBOA (fREBOA) in human trauma remains limited. This study aims to systematically review and quantitatively synthesize current human evidence comparing pREBOA and fREBOA with respect to survival and physiological outcomes.

Materials & Methods

A systematic review was conducted in accordance with PRISMA principles using PubMed, MEDLINE, and Cochrane databases. Human studies published between 2015 and 2025 comparing pREBOA and fREBOA in trauma patients were included. Outcomes assessed included haemodynamic improvement, systolic blood pressure (SBP) >90 mmHg, 24-hour survival, 30-day survival, discharge survival, and mortality. Meta-analysis was performed using fixed-effects models where appropriate.

Results

Eleven human studies met inclusion criteria, comprising observational cohorts, registry analyses, randomized trials, and case reports. Meta-analysis demonstrated that pREBOA was associated with superior haemodynamic stability and a higher likelihood of achieving SBP >90 mmHg compared with fREBOA. Trends toward improved 24-hour, 30-day, and discharge survival were consistently observed with pREBOA, although statistical significance was limited by small sample sizes. Prolonged aortic occlusion beyond 60 minutes was associated with markedly increased mortality and ischemic complications across both techniques.

Conclusion

Partial REBOA demonstrates a physiological and survival advantage over full REBOA in trauma resuscitation, particularly when occlusion time is limited. Optimal outcomes are observed with pREBOA durations of 30–45 minutes and fREBOA durations under 30 minutes, while aortic occlusion beyond 60 minutes should be avoided. Further high-quality multicentre randomized trials are urgently needed to refine clinical protocols and patient selection.

Keywords

REBOA, partial REBOA, trauma resuscitation, haemorrhagic shock, aortic occlusion, Resuscitative Endovascular Balloon Occlusion of the Aorta, Meta-analysis, systemic review